

DIABETES MELLITUS - SYMPTOMS, COMPLICATIONS, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

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Annotation: Alternative areas of medicine, which together make up the so—called complementary medicine (translated from English "complementary medicine"), are those types of health improvement practices that are used in conjunction with officially recognized methods. More and more doctors are inclined to combine traditional (accepted by modern medicine based on evidence) methods of treatment with non-traditional, including herbal medicine. Complementary medicine is currently being actively researched and developed in America and Europe.

Keywords: chronic renal, correct dosage, hypoglycemic drugs

The most reputable organizations in this field are the National Cancer Institute (USA), the National Center for Complementary and Alternative Medicine (USA), the MD Anderson Center, and the Institute of Complementary Medicine (UK). The prospects for the further development of complementary medicine are beyond doubt, as this area includes thousands of years of experience accumulated by many generations of healers and doctors.

The study of possible side effects of various hypoglycemic drugs noted in scientific studies has shown that most synthetic hypoglycemic agents cause numerous complications. These include the development of hypoglycemia (hypoglycemic shock), diabetic ketoacidosis, increased risk of bone fractures, drug intolerance, and increased risk of urinary tract infections, increased body weight, increased risk of heart failure, heart attacks, strokes and even oncological pathology. It is emphasized that it is impossible to use certain drugs in chronic renal and liver

failure, diseases of the nervous and respiratory systems, in elderly patients and motor vehicle drivers.

The article by M.V. Shestakova noted the development of endothelial dysfunction in metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance (IR). In this regard, the need to use medicines that could directly or indirectly restore the normal function of endothelial cells in order to prevent the development of cardiovascular diseases and provide anti-atherogenic effects was emphasized. Modern medicine faces the need to develop new drugs that would help achieve stable metabolic states in order to reduce the risk of side effects and dysfunction of pancreatic b cells.

The safety of medicines is of paramount importance. The requirements increase from year to year, however, a long period of follow-up is necessary for a real assessment of therapeutic efficacy and the development of side effects. For synthetic drugs, it is difficult to find a balance between positive therapeutic effects and their side effects, since patients have been forced to take medications for years. When using synthetic drugs, it is difficult to use an individual approach, taking into account the personal characteristics of the individual, to monitor safety and the development of side effects.

The basis of Avicenna medicines intended for pathogenetic and auxiliary therapy of various degrees and forms of diabetes were herbal, mineral and animal products with alkalizing properties, which determined the essence of the "opposite to opposite" therapy tactics. Due to this, each of these drugs, with the correct dosage, was able to change the reaction of the acid-base state (pH) of the patient's body from acidic to neutral or slightly alkaline.

Diabetes mellitus is a non-communicable epidemic, which is one of the most dangerous challenges to all mankind in the 21st century. As in the whole world, the number of patients in Russia is mainly increasing due to type 2 diabetes mellitus. According to official data, the number of diabetic patients in Russia exceeds 2.66 million people; according to epidemiological studies, the real number of patients

with diabetes in our country is 3-4 times higher. Awareness of this fact determines for specialists a modern therapeutic strategy to combat diabetes: to prevent and control the progression of the disease and its associated risks as effectively as possible. The development of tactics for the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in recent years has become one of the most urgent and difficult tasks of modern medicine.

Currently developed incretin-based drugs are glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) agonists and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors. They have taken their place in the therapeutic paradigm of type 2 diabetes mellitus. The class of DPP-4 inhibitors is represented today by oral drugs, sitagliptin and vildagliptin, which have entered Russian clinical practice. In the class of agonists of the GPP-1 receptors, there are currently two classes of drugs in the world. Exenatide, a synthetic agonist of the GPP-1 receptors isolated from the saliva of the giant lizard Gila Monster, has been introduced into clinical practice. The drug is intended for 2-fold injection. However, it is only 53% homologous to the native human GLP-1. Later, liraglutide came into world clinical practice – the first of the class of analogues of human GLP-1, a drug intended for administration once a day, which is so far the only incretinomimetic 97% identical to human GLP-1. The unique homology of liraglutide with human GLP-1 allows us to count on the acquisition of all the positive properties of native GLP-1 by liraglutide, and, importantly, low antibody formation. The possibility of using the drug both in monotherapy and in combination with any PSP, and a convenient mode of administration – once a day, regardless of food intake, certainly complements the range of positive properties of liraglutide.

The 3rd phase of the international multicenter clinical trial program LEAD (Effects and effects of liraglutide in diabetes) included more than 4,000 patients with type 2 diabetes and was carried out in 600 centers in 41 countries, including Russia. Liraglutide was compared with both placebo and existing widely used hypoglycemic drugs. In 2009, for the first time at the Congress of the American Diabetes

Association, the results of a meta-analysis of the LEAD 1-6 studies were presented. Meta-analysis convincingly demonstrates the non-glycemic effects of the drug: liraglutide, in comparison with other hypoglycemic drugs, provides a more effective target achievement of the final complex, combining three extremely important parameters of successful therapy: HbA1c, systolic blood pressure and body weight.

The embodiment in therapeutic practice of the potential impact of native GLP-1 on cardiovascular risk factors (pro-inflammatory markers, endothelial dysfunction), and, in general, the cardioprotective effect, hopefully opens a new stage in the therapy of type 2 diabetes. Given the significant effect on body weight, liraglutide is also under study for the treatment of obesity in humans, in doses up to 3 mg per day. In 2009 For the first time, the results of treatment of obese patients without diabetes mellitus were published, where it was shown that liraglutide reduces the likelihood of impaired tissue tolerance to glucose in overweight people and contributes to the normalization of carbohydrate metabolism during 20 weeks of therapy in most obese patients. This special issue of the journal analyzes the clinical profile of the efficacy and safety of liraglutide based on the results of clinical studies; reviews and opinions of leading international experts in the field of diabetes are presented.

The diagnosis should be made as early as possible, because diabetes mellitus leads to the development of various diseases: diabetic microangiopathy (damage to the retina and kidneys), diabetic neuropathy (damage to nerve endings), diabetic foot syndrome, diabetic macroangiopathies (coronary heart disease, chronic heart failure, cerebrovascular diseases, atherosclerosis of the arteries of the lower extremities), obesity, hypertension.

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